

ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF JOB STRESSORS ON JOB SATISFACTION OF PRIVATE BANK EMPLOYEES AT WOLAITA ZONE, ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT

Job stress may be referred to the body's reaction to a change that requires a physical, mental or emotional adjustment or response to work responsibilities. Job stress is considered as the harmful physical and emotional response that occurs when there is a poor match between job demand and capability, resource or need of the employee. Job satisfaction describes how comfortable an individual is with own job. The objective of the research is to examine the effect of job stress and job stressors on job satisfaction among employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. Based on review of literature conceptual framework for this study was designed. Job stress factors include Work overload, Role conflict, Role ambiguity, Physical environment, Superior support, Peer support are taken as independent variables and Satisfaction of employees with the job is dependent variable. The study has been conducted on the basis of the primary data collected through structured questionnaire. The research design has been taken to be causal. The measurement scale for the instrument is considered five point Likert scale representing the intervals. The study is being carried out at eleven private banks situated at Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. The study was conducted between Sep, 2017 and Jan, 2018. The population of this study is the employees working in branches of six private banks located at Wolaita zone. There were total 254 employees working in these branches which constitute the respondents of the study. Out of total population of 254 employees working in eleven banks' branches only 216 employees could be contacted, so the study incorporates the responses of these 216 bank employees. The regression result shows that Work overload, Role conflict, Superior support and Peer support have significant predictor of job satisfaction of employees of private banks while physical environment and Role ambiguity are not the significant predictor of job satisfaction of employees of private banks. Out of six job stressors Superior support followed by Peer support is strongest predictor of employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommendation that for improving job satisfaction the superior must support their subordinates in solving their problems as well as the work problems. The superiors should try to create the environment of peer cooperation. Closer relationships among employees may result in more social support at work. Cooperative organizational culture and supervisor's attention to employees will be effective in enhancing job satisfaction. The superior should try to lessen the work overload at individual level by properly distributing the work among employees.

Key words: Job Stress, Work Overload, Role Conflict, Role Ambiguity, Job Autonomy, Relationship at Work, Physical Environment, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Organizations play a very significant role in the economy and for the country's development. Earning goodwill and profit in a high level is the main purpose for which an organisation is established. For this purpose, the organisations are needed to make sure whether the employees who are working in their organisations in various positions and jobs are satisfied or not. Employee job satisfaction is necessary criteria for any organisation's growth and development. It is a crucial and key part for any organisation. In any organisation we find many people who are working for the sake of earning an income or money for themselves and profits for the organisation. If the workers of any organization are not satisfied with their work and feel stress on their jobs then the employees of the organization will have negative impact on the goodwill of the organization.

Working is the essence of every human being and most part of everyday lives of human being is spent on working. Working and its various aspects and effects on lives of the human beings have been investigated by many researchers. Working for anyone is to meet a number of basic human necessities related to mental and physical exercise, social bonding, self-esteem, self-confidence and feelings of competence or qualification apart from earning an income. However, it may also be a source of major psychological pressure and stress (Khodayarifard M, Parand A. 2001). In psychology, stress is defined as being under psychological pressure. Stress is the cause and a feeling of fear, excitement, anxiety, danger or anger in an individual's state of mind and is the human being body reciprocation to physical, mental and chemical response to the events (Hashemzade I, Orangi M, Bahredar Mohammad J, 2000).

The competitive nature of the work environment has led to most of the people in the world to spend most their time for job related working purposes. Stress is a condition which happens when a person realizes the pressure on him or the requirement of any situation is wider than he can handle, and if such requirements are huge and it continues for a very long period of time without having any interval, it results in occurrence of mental, physical or behavioral problems. In the field of physical science the term stress has a different meaning. It is the force which is placed upon an object to cause damage, bending, or breaking. In case of human beings, stress is used to describe the body's responses to favourability or unfavourability when the demands are placed upon the body. Anything that causes stress is called a stressor.

The banking industry is the most important constituent of the financial sector of any economy. Banking industry in Ethiopia has undergone a tremendous amount of changes during the past few years. With the opening of the banking sector, there is stiff competition between public sector banks, private sector and foreign banks. It is in this context, banks understood that capital and technology are replicable but not human capital which is a valuable resource for achieving a competitive edge. The intense competition in introduction of innovative products and

services and for the banks to satisfy the divergent customer needs has created more demand and pressures on employees of the banks to thereby increases stress vulnerability.

In developed and developing countries, one of the most important workplace health risks for employees is Job stress (Rehman, Irum, Tahir, Ijaz, Noor, Salma, 2012). Stressors are usually associated with inter-personal relationships at work, like conflicts with the superiors, conflicts with peers, conflicts with lower designation people and differences with the management and their policies (Adeoye, 2002). Stress is a situation related to environment which requires a person to perform the tasks that may be beyond the capability and ability of a person and resources for meeting it. Sometimes a person may expect a major difference in the rewards system to meet the personal demand versus not able to meet it (McGrath, 1976). Extreme stress in working life is so intense to employees that in order to avoid it they show psychological factors like disinterest in work or job involvement will reduce to a great extent, and it leads to physically factors like frequent late coming, absenteeism, laziness etc. and sometimes by leaving the job itself (Beehr and Newman, 1978).

At the place of work there are many job stressor factors that make jobs stressful and difficult for number of employees who are in services as well as manufacturing industries. Some of the job stressor factors are overload of work, ambiguity in the roles, conflicts with the superiors, conflict in roles, conflicts with peers, conflicts with subordinates and conflicts with the management and regarding their policies (Mansoor et al., 2011). Job stress is multidimensional in nature like workload pressure, performance pressure, work family conflict, role conflict, time pressure, ambiguity in the roles, autonomy in jobs, physical working environment etc. (Khaak, 2004). When employees are at the place of the work, there are different types of stressors which have a direct impact on the employees performance (Azizollah et al., 2013).

Employee's job satisfaction is important for both the employee and the industry. Motivation will be high to do their jobs and to make them more productive if the employees are satisfied. The factor for the success and profitability of an organisation or an industry is the satisfaction of employees who are the working force. If the employees are dissatisfied, it may lead to their inefficiency, and result in the intention to leave the organization. Employee with higher job satisfaction are very important as they believe that the organization would have a tremendous future in the long run and the employer gives credit to the quality of their work. Such employee will become more committed to the organization which results to have higher retention rates leading to have higher productivity (Ayub and Rafif, 2011).

Job satisfaction considered in terms of an employee's overall satisfaction with their job as a multidimensional construct. In the works of Hirschfeld, (2000) job satisfaction is concerned with satisfaction with pay, supervision, company policy and the nature of the work. Job satisfaction consists of the extrinsic and intrinsic components where Intrinsic job satisfaction is related to how people feel about the nature of the job tasks, whereas Extrinsic job satisfaction is related to how people feel about the various aspects of the work situations which are external to the tasks of the job (Hirschfeld, 2000).

For every organization employee performance, employee engagement and job satisfaction are very important. Other variables such as intellectual abilities, physical abilities, employees qualification, reward systems, culture, experience, training, career advancement opportunities, peer support and behaviour, authority and responsibility, work overload and structure of the organization also affect these attitudes. Work overload is the main problem faced by the employees in practice. Every employee faces work overload and this leads to stress at work and also personal life which ultimately affects their performance and job satisfaction (Shah, 2011, Sobiya and Farooqi, 2014).

High work related stress has been one of the major reasons for job dissatisfaction and poor work performances (Ismail and Tan, 2011). According to Schultz and Schultz, (1994), job dissatisfaction is most likely caused by occupational stress. An employee, who is dissatisfied with her/his job, dislikes coming to work and finds little reason for doing well on the job. Individuals who report being very satisfied with their jobs, do not suffer from harmful effects of stress. Those employees who are not satisfied with their jobs do show stress-related effects.

Around the globe especially in case of banking employees, job stress has become a real challenge. Stress is dual that is sometimes it can be positive or sometimes it can be negative. Positive stress is one which leads to productivity and negative stress leads to loss for the individual and also for the organization. A certain level of stress exists in the work life of banking employees which leads them encountering even more stress arising from the work pressure which banking employees face on the job. It is very difficult for most of the employees to cope with such rapid changes taking place in their jobs. This study, therefore, looks into the relationship between job stressors and satisfaction with job among the employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The objective of the research is to examine the effect of job stress and job stressors on job satisfaction among employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The two significant focuses in human resource management researches are job satisfaction and job stress. Job stress is a pervasive problem, which affects all professional and occupational groups of the individuals in society. It causes a lot of mental and physical illness. Furthermore, it is costly to organizations and companies due to reduced performance of the employees, increased absence from work, medical costs and disability of the workers and funding for new recruitment (Enjezab B, Farnia F,2001)

Employees stress is a growing concern for organizations today. Stress can be defined as a lively circumstance in which people face loss of something they desire, there are constraints for opportunities and for which the consequence is both crucial as well as unpredictable. It is also

the response of people to the excessive pressure and unreasonable demands which are placed on them. Stress is a perception of a stimulus and a natural physical response which has an evolutionary purpose and the need is to protect and innate 'Flight to fight' aspects of nervous system when battling for survival. The stress that exists is the stimulus which can be something of physical like emotions, fear of losing a job or getting embarrassed at the place of work. It does not mean that all the sources of stress should be negative stimuli as some of the sources of stress may actually be happy events.

Some of the symptoms of stress at workplace are as follows-

- Absenteeism, not ready to take any work responsibilities, being late or leaving early from the work place etc.
- Decrease in the performance of work, increase in error prone work, memory loss, etc.
- Cribbing about the work , sometimes over-reacting or arguing with others, getting easily irritated, showing anxiety, etc.
- Health hazards, chances of accidents, etc.
- Improper food habits like over-eating or under-eating, smoking and alcohol habits, state of sleeplessness, etc.

Caral Lopes, DharaKachalia, (2016) have conducted a study on the private and public banks. Their study has shown that the growth of technology has revolutionized the way banking sector functions and the economic conditions have increased the globalized competition. This has lead the employees especially in the banking sector for facing a growth in high stress levels. The study found that there is a significant relationship between the type of the banks and other factors like age, gender and education, role of the job, inter-personal relationship and impact of occupational stress. The banking sector employees should adopt new coping strategies for maintaining good physical and mental condition to improve productivity.

Kishori&Vinothini (2016) the authors have found that productivity of the work force is decisive factor for the success of an organization is concerned. In the present age of high competition and dynamic world, an employee who is working is exposed to many kinds of stressors which can affect them on all realms of life. The research intended to study the impact of occupational stress on Nationalized Bank employees.

Priyanka Das, Alok Kumar Srivastav (2015) have in their study identified that banks must manage people who are working to improve the physical work environment. It is the organizations which has to enhance the psychological well-being of the employees and their health, which leads to increase in the organizational revenues and there will be retention of the employee as well. "A Healthy Employee is a Productive Employee to any organisation", they concluded that the level of stress among the selected public sector banks are found to be limited and the management should take necessary steps to help the employees to relieve the stress and

also help to impact more productive employees that will help the banks to achieve greater heights.

The most frequently researched variable in organizational behavior has been Job satisfaction which means how much people feel positive about their jobs at the workplace (Spector, 1997). An important indicator for low job satisfaction can lead to decrease in productivity and morale of the employee and can result in adverse behavior such as absenteeism (Martin & Miller, 1986) and turnover intentions (Dupre & Day, 2007). The previous studies suggest that higher level of job stress causes less job satisfaction (K. Chandraiah, S.C. Agrawal, P. Marimuthu & N. Manoharan 2003).

Several studies have tried to determine the link between stress and job satisfaction. The stress will be affected by number of stressors. Role conflict is amongst one of the important factors which causes stress. It has a significant negative impact on job satisfaction. (David Yong Gun Fie, Syed Shah Alam, Zaini Abdullah and Nilufar Ahsan, 2009). Workload and professional uncertainty are other factors affecting employee job satisfaction negatively. (Laura McCann, Carmel M. Hughes, Colin G. Adair and Chris Cardwell, 2009).

Correlation analysis of a study made by Vanishree and Ganapathi, (2013) indicates that the employee job satisfaction has negative and significant relationship with workload and role conflict. The study also revealed that while physical environment and employee job satisfaction are positively and significantly correlated with in small-scale industries. It was established that a strong negative significant relationship existed between occupational stress and job satisfaction. Organizational aspects, long work hours, lack of organizational support and organizational change (Davey, et al., 2001), lack of support from supervisors and colleagues, and conflict with demands and pressures (Leka, et al., 2004) also lead to Job stress.

A study which was conducted on the naval personnel in Malaysia examined the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction. The results showed that job stress was negatively associated with the eight factors of job satisfaction (Nor Liyana Mohd Boki and Mansor Abu Talib, 2009). In the same case of air force military pilots revealed that the people working in any type of organization are affected by stress which ultimately affects their job performance. According to a study of air force military pilots in the case of Iran, job stress reduces job satisfaction. (Khodabakhsh Ahmadi and Kolivand Alireza, 2007). Occupational stress has a direct and negative effect on job satisfaction (Noordin Yahaya, Azizi Yahaya, Farhana Amat Tamyas, Jasmi Ismail & Saini Jaalam 2010). Bemana et al. (2013) study reported that negative relationship existed between occupational stress and satisfaction of the job. Similarly, most findings have also reported inverse relationships between job stress and job satisfaction (Beehr et al., 1976; Hawe et al., 2000).

The constructs of job satisfaction and job stress have been treated as related yet distinct. Job stress has been viewed as a predecessor of job satisfaction (Stanton, Bachiochi, Robie, Perez,

& Smith, 2002). According to Stamps & Piedmonte (1986) job satisfaction was found to have significant relationship with job stress. Other organizational factors such as workload and working condition were found to be negatively related with job satisfaction (Vinokur-Kaplan 1991). The dissatisfaction of any factor can be a source of stress, while high satisfaction can lighten the effects of stress it means that both job stress and job satisfaction are interrelated and interdependent (Fletcher & Payne 1980).

VARIABLES IDENTIFICATION

Based on the discussion in literature review following factors are identified for our research

Work overload: The situation in which someone has too much work to do. It happens when job demands exceed an individual's ability to deal with them. It represents the weight of hours, the sacrifice of time, and the sense of frustration with the inability to complete tasks in the time given. The study findings from the works of Kayastha and Kayastha (2012) revealed high occupational stress is the cause of heavy workload, strenuous working conditions, poor peer relations, unreasonable group and political pressure among staff. Chan et al. (2000) recounted that employees were most likely to experience work overload in educational settings. Most study findings have reported that work overload and job satisfaction are inversely related (Bemana et al., 2013).

Role conflict : Role conflict occurs when incompatible demands are placed upon a person in such a way that compliance with both would be difficult to handle. Role conflict is experienced by people when they find that they are pulled in various directions as they try to respond to the many statuses they hold. Role conflict is an important job stressor which is faced due to performance of different roles a person is expected to perform (Butler & Constantine, 2005). Role conflict may start when two or more concurrent and unsuited expectations exist in such a way that the agreement with a given role compromises for fulfilling the other roles (Drury, 1984; Thompson & Powers, 1983). For both men and women role conflict decreases job satisfaction (Coverman 1989). Those workers who have a high centrality of the family role are prone to work role conflict leading to a greater impact on job satisfaction (Carlson and Kacmar, 2000). Role conflict involves contradiction in expectations of an employee position. This may occur when a sales person is given a variety of contrary orders or is given a range of responsibilities that cannot be completed all together (Brashear et al., 2003).

Role ambiguity: Role ambiguity occurs when people are not clear or certain about their work or role expectations, typically related to their role at the job or place of work. Role ambiguity arises when the definition of the person's job is not defined properly or clearly. Traditional theories of role stress reveals that role stress is directly related and is the cause for job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, and turnover intentions (Malik, Waheed and Malik, 2010; Ling, Bahron and Boroh, 2014). In the research study Bashir and Ramay (2010) viewed role which lacks proper information related to duties to be performed, the role and responsibility, the powers and authority associated to perform one's role is termed as role ambiguity. Various research studies

have identified negative relationship existing between role ambiguity and job satisfaction (Rizzo, House, & Lirtzman 1970; Van Sell, Brief, & Schuler 1981; Fisher & Gitelson, 1983; Jackson & Schuler, 1985; Singh 1998).

Physical environment : The part of the human *environment* that includes *physical* factors such as spacious buildings, proper ventilation, availability of water facilities, plants and animals, and all the other infrastructure, and all of the natural resources that provide for the basic needs and opportunities for required for social and economic development. Physical environment can be defined in terms of lightening, noise, temperature, humidity, clean air, air circulation and exposure to dangerous substances. McGinty (2007) reported that stress at the workplace leads to reduction in productivity, increase in management pressure and make the workers sick in different ways. Stress causes loss of efficiency, increased employee absenteeism and unexplained problems (Marilyn, 2003). The opinion of Igbal and Waseem (2012) is that stress is not necessarily a negative phenomenon; it is often associated with interaction between humans and their environment. Further implying that the stress itself is affected by a number of stressors

Superior support: Superior support is defined as the extent to which leaders value their employees' contributions and care about their well-being. A leader with high superior support is the one who makes employees feel that they are heard, valued, and cared about at the work place. Some research studies have shown that a positive relationship exists between satisfaction of the job and supervision. (Peterson, Puia & Suess, 2003; Smucker, Whisenant & Pedersen, 2003; Mafini & Dlodlo, 2013). Robbins (2003) reveals that supervision forms a critical role in relating to job satisfaction. The job satisfaction also arises when the superior has the ability to provide technical and emotional help and guidance on the work related duties and activities. This suggests that superiors contribute to high level or low morale levels of the employees at the place of the work (Ramsey, 1997). According to Dyk and Coetzee (2012) who have opined, that supervisor support includes the recognition and feedback that employees receive from their supervisors. Most research studies have reported the importance of recognition and feedback for retaining valuable employees (Allen, Shore & Griffeth, 2003; Morrow, 2011).

Peer support: It means support from colleagues regarding work-related issues. Peers can cushion the stress responses people might otherwise experience when their jobs are demanding. Interpersonal relationships and friendships at the workplace are formed due to the fact that employees spend major part of their lives at the work place, Hamilton (2007). In his research reported that people are likely to receive assistance, advice, guidance, recommendations, feedback, or information from work related issues such as performing tasks, competing job demands and handling matters with superiors, colleagues, subordinates, or customers. A related study on job stress, associated with co-worker support and job satisfaction also revealed that there was high level of stress experienced in the job and is positively, strongly, and significantly associated with the dependent variable (Gul & Delice, 2011)

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on review of literature conceptual framework for this study was designed. Job stress factors include Work overload, Role conflict, Role ambiguity, Physical environment, Superior support, Peer support are taken as independent variables and Satisfaction of employees with the job is dependent variable (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

The functional form of the model will be;

$$JS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 JSt$$

$$JS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WOL + \beta_2 RC + \beta_3 RA + \beta_4 PE + \beta_5 SS + \beta_6 PS + \mu$$

Where; Y- represents job satisfaction.

β_0 – is the intercept term

β_1 – β_6 - Regression Coefficients of independent variables

JS – Job satisfaction

JSt – Job stress

WOL – Work overload

RC – Role conflict

RA – Role ambiguity

PE – Physical environment

SS – Superior support

PS – Peer support

μ – It is the stochastic disturbance term

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

In light of the objectives articulated above, the following hypotheses were investigated:

H₁: Work overload as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

H₂: Role conflict as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

H₃: Role ambiguity as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

H₄: Physical environment as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

H₅: Superior support as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

H₆: Peer support as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study has been conducted on the basis of the primary data collected through structured questionnaire. As the approach aims at analysing the Effect of Job Stress determinant on Job Satisfaction, the research design has been taken to be causal. The measurement scale for the instrument is considered five point Likert scale representing the intervals. The study is being carried out at eleven private banks situated at Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. The population of this study is the employees working in branches of six private banks located at Wolaita zone. There were total 254 employees working in these branches which constitute the respondents of the study. In the pilot study, reliability of the questionnaire was maintained (Cronbach alpha = .919).

ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

Out of total population of 254 employees working in eleven banks' branches only 216 employees could be contacted, so the study incorporates the responses of these 216 bank employees.

In the outcome of the research relating to job stress and job satisfaction, there is very strong correlation between job stress of bank employees and their job satisfaction.(table 1). When we correlate job stress determinants with job satisfaction we find that all determinants of job stress correlates significantly with job satisfaction of bank employees. (table 2)

Table 1: Correlation of Job stress of bank employees with job satisfaction

		Job satisfaction	Job Stress
Customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	-.711**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 2: Correlation of Job stress determinants with job satisfaction of bank employees

	Customer satisfaction
Customer satisfaction	1
Work overload	-.364**
Role conflict	-.453**
Role ambiguity	-.350**
Physical Environment	.313*
Superior support	.640**
Peer support	.531**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 depicts the model summary when we regress job stress on job satisfaction. It shows that job stress explains 50.6% variability on job satisfaction. This shows that besides job stress 49.4% of the factors which are not covered by this study also have an impact on customer satisfaction. This also opens the scope of future research. The difference between R^2 And adjusted R^2 is .001 which is very less; it means that the model can be generalized for total population i.e. employees of all private banks.

When we research the impact of job stress determinants (Work overload, Role conflict, Role ambiguity, Physical Environment, Superior support and Peer support) on job satisfaction of bank employees, we see that the all independent variables explain 54.6% variability on job satisfaction (table 4).

Table 3: Regression model summary (Job stress with job satisfaction)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.711	.506	.505	.48784

Table 4: Regression model summary (Job stress determinants with job satisfaction)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.739	.546	.539	.47051

Table 5 shows analysis of variance of job satisfaction by job stress of bank employees. As the F value is significant (Sig = .000) at even 99.99% confidence level we can predict that job stress significantly effects job satisfaction of bank employees.

Table 5: ANOVA of Job satisfaction by Job stress of bank employees

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	87.750	1	87.750	368.719	.000
Residual	85.675	214	.238		
Total	173.425	215			

Table 6: ANOVA of Job satisfaction by Job stress determinants of bank employees

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	94.613	6	18.923	85.475	.000
Residual	78.812	209	.221		
Total	173.425	215			

Table 5 states that F value is on very higher side and p value is .000 which shows that model explains significant variability of job satisfaction by six job stress determinants of bank employees.

Table 7: Regression coefficients of Job stress taking job satisfaction as dependent variable

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.144	.369		3.100	.000
Job stress	-1.447	.065	.711	-22.261	.000

Table 7 shows the regression coefficients taking job stress as independent variable. The customer satisfaction increase by 1.144, if stress is not present and that increase is significant also. One unit increase in perceived job stress leads to 1.447 unit decrease in job satisfaction and this increase is significant. It shows that job stress among bank employees significantly reducing job satisfaction (.000 = sig < .05 at 95% confidence level).

Regression model can be summarized as:

$$JS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 JS_t$$

$$JS = 1.144 - 1.447JS_t$$

Table 8: Regression coefficients of Job stress determinants taking job satisfaction as dependent variable

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.035	.393		2.633	.009
Work overload	- 0.169	.063	.105	-2.662	.008
Role conflict	- 0.119	.056	.092	-2.129	.034
Role ambiguity	- 0.049	.025	.068	-1.956	.055
Physical Environment	0.002	.072	.001	.026	.979
Superior support	0.505	.065	.408	7.749	.000
Peer support	0.386	.068	.299	5.656	.000

Table 8 shows the regression coefficients of six bank employees job stress determinants as independent variables the customer satisfaction increase by 1.035 if job stressors are not present and that increase is significant also. The effect of each job stress determinants (independent variables) can be discussed simultaneously by taking each result by keeping others not changing (constant). For example one unit increase in perceived work overload leads to .169 unit decrease in job satisfaction and this decrease is significant. The table shows that superior support and peer support are highest contributor towards job satisfaction of private bank employees ($t = 7.749$ and $t = 5.656$) while physical environment has least ($t = .026$) and that is insignificant also. Physical environment is even not remotely predict job satisfaction.

Regression model can be summarized as:

$$JS = 1.035 - 0.169WOL - 0.119RC + 0.505SS + 0.386PS$$

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

From table 8 the six hypothesis of the research can be tested as follows.

H₁: Work overload as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is accepted as $p = .008 (< .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

H₂: Role conflict as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is accepted as $p = .034 (< .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

H₃: Role ambiguity as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is rejected as $p = .055 (> .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

H₄: Physical environment as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is rejected as $p = .979 (> .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

H₅: Superior support as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is accepted as $p = .000 (< .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

H₆: Peer support as stressor has significant predictor of job satisfaction of private bank employees in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia, the hypothesis is accepted as $p = .000 (< .05)$ at 95% level of confidence.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study was conducted to examine the effect of job stress and job stressors on job satisfaction among employee of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. With respect to the specific hypotheses and empirical findings emerged from the investigation. The findings of the research indicate that job stressors like Work overload, Role conflict, Role ambiguity and Physical environment correlates with job satisfaction moderately and Work overload, Role conflict and Role ambiguity negatively associated with job satisfaction. Superior support and Peer support correlates positively and strongly with job satisfaction of employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. The regression result shows that Work overload, Role conflict, Superior support and Peer support have significant predictor of job satisfaction of employees of private banks while physical environment and Role ambiguity are not the significant predictor of job satisfaction of employees of private banks. Out of six job stressors Superior support followed by Peer support is strongest predictor of employees of private banks in Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. Out of six hypotheses four are accepted and two are rejected.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommendation that for improving job satisfaction the superior must support their subordinates in solving their problems as well as the work problems. The superiors should try to create the environment of peer peer cooperation. Closer relationships among employees may result in more social support at work. Cooperative organizational culture and supervisor's attention to employees will be effective in enhancing job satisfaction. The superior should try to lessen the work overload at individual level by properly distributing the work among employees.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This research however has more rooms for further research. Further research could be conducted to public bank in same area as well as in other regions of Ethiopia to generalize the findings. Further the researchers have to find other factors besides covered in this research and conduct the research as these unidentified factors also constitute large grey area (nearly 50%).

Same kind of research can be extended to other groups like Doctors, nurses, lawyers, teachers etc. to generalize the findings of this research.

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